

The Effect of Capsaicin on Tomato Seed Germination

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Presentation Overview

01. Introduction

02. Hypotheses & Predictions

03. Experimental Methods

04. Discussion

01

Introduction

Introduction

1) Big Picture

→ Rationale

- Capsaicin as a growth medium is less intensive than harmful chemicals
- Large-scale capsaicin use could limit potential adverse effects for consumers

→ Behind the Design

- Wood ash as a comparative treatment, carries nutrients and studies have been done showing positive effects for seed germination
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02

Hypothesis and Predictions

Hypotheses & Predictions

1) Hypotheses

→ **Alternative:** Capsaicin-treated soil will increase seed germination in tomato seeds because of its inherent antifungal and allelopathic properties.

→ **Null:** Capsaicin-treated soil will have no statistically significant effect on tomato seed germination

2) Predictions

→ Frequency of sprouted seeds will be higher in capsaicin-treated soil within 8-10 day time frame of tomato seed germination as compared to wood ash-treated and non-treated soil

03

Experimental Methods

Methodology

1.) Sample Design:

→ Groups:

- 2% w/v capsaicin solution + soil
- 5% w/v wood ash solution + soil
- Only soil

→ Sample size:

- 108 samples – (36 cells*3 trays=108)

→ Replicates:

- 35 replicates per treatment

2.) Equipment:

- Micropipette, funnel, coffee filter paper, 100% organic cayenne powder, wood ash, tape, drip trays + cells, grow light, graduated cylinder, beakers, analytical balance, popsicle stick, measuring tape.

3.) Data Analysis

→ Two-tailed T-test assuming equal variances

- XLMiner Analysis Toolpak
- Vars. to be collected: # of successfully germinated seed, treatment type (control, capsaicin, wood-ash).

04

Discussion

Potential Experimental Results

- ❑ Faster average germination time with capsaicin treatment
- ❑ No difference in germination time between treatments and control
- ❑ Faster germination in control or wood ash treatment

Results and Real World Application

Home Gardeners

Easy and inexpensive way to increase crop yield

Agricultural Producers

Healthier alternative to chemical growth mediums

Consumers

Good quality produce without harsh chemicals applied

Rejection of Hypothesis

- ❑ Results show higher plant growth and germination rate for control plants
- ❑ Plants with capsaicin-treated soil do not grow
- ❑ Plant growth does not occur

What We Hope to Learn

- ❑ Do natural ways of improving crop growth actually work?
- ❑ In what observable ways does capsaicin affect plants?

Thank you!
Any questions?

